

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18644073>

ETIOTROPIC THERAPY OF ACUTE DIARRHEAL INFECTIONS IN CHILDREN

Rashidov F.A.

Tashkent State Medical University
Department of Infectious Diseases, Pediatric Infections, Phthisiology and Pulmonology

ABSTRACT

It has been revealed that antibacterial drugs have been widely used for the treatment of acute intestinal infection, the effectiveness of which has not been proven against the causative agent of acute intestinal infection (rifampicin, cephalosporins of the first and second generation, lincomycin, penicillin). Their unjustifiably widespread use forms the resistance of pathogens, which means that it reduces their effectiveness in the treatment of acute intestinal infections.

Keywords: antibacterial therapy, acute intestinal infections in children.

ЭТИОТРОПНАЯ ТЕРАПИЯ ОСТРЫХ ДИАРЕЙНЫХ ИНФЕКЦИИ У ДЕТЕЙ

Рашидов Ф.А.

Ташкентский государственный медицинский университет
Кафедра инфекционных болезней, детских инфекций, фтизиатрии и пульмонологии

АННОТАЦИЯ

Выявлено, что для лечения острой кишечной инфекции широко использовались антибактериальные препараты, эффективность которых в отношении возбудителя острой кишечной инфекции не доказана (рифампицин, цефалоспорины I и II поколения, линкомицин, пенициллин). Неоправданно широкое их применение формирует резистентность патогенов, а значит, снижает их эффективность при лечении острых кишечных инфекций

Ключевые слова: антибактериальная терапия, острые кишечные инфекции у детей.

БОЛАЛАРДА ЎТКИР ДИАРЕЯ КАСАЛЛИКЛАРИНИ ЭТИОТРОП ДАВОЛАШ

Рашидов Ф.А.

Тошкент Давлат Тиббиёт Университети

Юқумли касалликлар, болалар юқумли касалликлар, фтизиатрия ва
пульмонология кафедраси

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ўткир ичак инфекциясини даволаш учун антибактериал препаратлар кенг қўлланилганлиги аниқланди, уларнинг самарадорлиги ўткир ичак инфекциясининг қўзғатувчисига (рифампицин, биринчи ва иккинчи авлод сефалоспоринлари, линкомицин, пенициллин) қарши исботланмаган. Уларнинг асосиз кенг қўлланилиши патогенларнинг қаршилигини шакллантиради, яъни бу уларнинг ўткир ичак инфекцияларини даволашда самарадорлигини пасайтиради.

Калит сўзлар: *антибактериал терапия, болаларда ўткир ичак инфекциялари.*

Relevance. Acute intestinal infections (AII) still occupy a leading place in the infectious pathology of children and adults, being second only to influenza and acute respiratory infections in terms of morbidity. The level of morbidity has remained consistently high over the past decade. This determines the paramount importance of comprehensive evaluation of diarrhea syndrome for early diagnosis and primary differential diagnosis of acute intestinal infections at the medical facility. During summer periods, maintaining health and preventing acute intestinal infections remains an urgent issue. In the overall structure of infectious and parasitic diseases, acute intestinal infections hold one of the highest positions. Cases are registered among all age groups of the population. Pediatric patients determine the incidence rate, accounting for 60% of the total number by age group. High levels of morbidity are recorded among unorganized children under two years old.

Objective of the study. The aim of this research was to investigate the clinical characteristics and antibiotic sensitivity of acute intestinal infections in young children living in hot climates. A multicenter pharmacological epidemiological analytical study was conducted with the goal of studying the choice of antibacterial therapy for acute intestinal infections in children. It turned out that during treatment of acute intestinal infections in children, antibiotics were used unnecessarily frequently. When choosing therapy, neither clinical symptoms nor severity of disease course were taken into

account. The selection of antibiotics indicates a low level of knowledge among doctors regarding the pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, and safety profile of antimicrobial drugs. Therefore, there is a need for continuous control over drug therapy choices, especially antibiotics, when treating children. To study existing practices for treating acute intestinal infection, we planned and carried out a multi-center pharmacological epidemiological analytical investigation aimed at studying strategies for antibacterial therapy in pediatric cases of acute intestinal infection.

Material and Methods. By means of complete sampling, case histories of children aged from several days to three years who received hospital care during seasonal peaks of acute intestinal infection morbidity between May-September and November-February in the period from 2020 to 2025 were analyzed. The study was conducted on the basis of Children's Infectious Hospital No. 4 in Tashkent city and the infectious departments of the Central District Hospital of Tashkent region. The following indicators were analyzed: patient's age, admission timeframe, disease severity, diagnosis of acute intestinal infection (clinical, bacteriological, serological), treatment strategy, choice of antibiotic therapy and other medications, routes of administration and duration of antibiotic therapy, outcomes of illness. Materials for the study included blood, urine, fecal samples. Research methods employed standard clinical laboratory examinations; extended bacteriological studies of diarrheal illnesses to establish etiologic structures, biochemical analyses. Data obtained were processed using computer program LRTL treatment evaluation descriptive statistics including the number of observations, frequency, and percentage share (% of total cases) for each analyzed indicator. **Results and Discussion.** A total of 142 case histories of acute intestinal infections in children aged 1 month to 15 years were analyzed. Among those affected, children aged 1 to 3 years predominated (30.8%), while hospitalization rates for children older than 3 years were twice as rare (14.4%). Infants younger than 1 year accounted for (81.3%) of admissions. In terms of nosological forms of acute intestinal infection, the distribution was as follows: invasive form—35.7%; secretory diarrhea—20.2%; viral diarrhea—18%; bacterial acute intestinal infections caused by opportunistic microflora—8%. Most children (63.8%) were admitted within the first 3 days of illness onset, but 46.2% arrived later. Diagnosis of acute intestinal infection based solely on clinical symptom presentation occurred in most instances (51.1%). Laboratory confirmation of acute intestinal infection (bacteriological, serological, virological) was performed in 48.8% of cases. Pathogen susceptibility testing was done in just 25.5% of cases where microbial isolation took place. However, the figure in Tashkent City itself was nearly three times higher (76.7%). Serological diagnostics for acute intestinal infection were found to be inadequate in the central district hospital of Tashkent region. As per analysis results, medium-severe forms dominated across all

centers (79.6%), particularly prevalent in the central district hospital of Tashkent region. Severe forms of acute intestinal infection occurred in 8.6% of cases in Tashkent City, whereas their prevalence in the regional hospital was 2.7 to 3.7 times higher than average. Milder courses of disease were noted in about 11.8% of cases, although these figures doubled in Tashkent City. Antibiotic use in treating acute intestinal infection averaged 88.5%. As shown by our findings, almost every child regardless of age or severity of illness received some form of antibiotic therapy. Antibiotics were prescribed less frequently in Tashkent City, where they constituted 59.5% of treatments. Combined antibiotic therapies involving two or even three different agents were administered in nearly half of cases (45.6%). Structurally, ineffective antibiotics made up 89.3% of prescriptions, including cephalosporins of the first and second generation, penicillins, lincomycin, aminoglycosides, chloramphenicol, sulfonamides, rifampin, and derivatives of 8-hydroxyquinoline. Only 10.7% of prescribed antibiotics had proven efficacy according to clinical trials, such as third-generation cephalosporins (3.8%), fluoroquinolones (6.2%), macrolides (0.7%). Susceptibility testing prior to selecting antibiotics was omitted in 74.5% of cases. On average, the duration of antibiotic therapy lasted 14.5 ± 5.0 days, ranging from 5 to 20 days. Most often, parenteral administration (61.1%) was preferred, mainly intramuscular injection, followed by oral intake (38%) and occasionally rectal application (0.1%). Findings indicate that antibiotics are commonly used in treating acute intestinal infections despite lacking effectiveness against causative organisms like shigellae. Unjustified broad-spectrum usage leads to resistance formation among enteropathogens, thereby reducing their therapeutic value. Key recommended antibiotics for treating shigellosis include quinolones (nalidixic acid), fluoroquinolones (ciprofloxacin, norfloxacin), macrolides (azithromycin), and third-generation cephalosporins.

Table №1. Frequency of antibiotic prescription depending on the etiology of acute intestinal infection.

Pathogen	Tashkent Region	Tashkent City
Shigellosis	91.7 %	100 %
Escherichia coli	60 %	100 %
Salmonellosis	100 %	90 %
Rotavirus infection	93.8 %	87.5 %
Opportunistic flora	100 %	100 %

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, the pharmaco-epidemiological study revealed that antibiotic use in treating acute intestinal infections in children is overly frequent without consideration of clinical symptomatology or disease severity. Chosen antibiotics reflect insufficient

understanding of pharmacodynamic properties, pharmacokinetic profiles, and safety features of antimicrobial agents. These factors underline the necessity for unified approaches towards managing acute intestinal infections in children and implementing educational programs for healthcare professionals

REFERENCES:

1. Особенности клинического течения сальмонеллезной инфекции у детей раннего возраста. Ибрагимова Х.Н. /Университетская наука: взгляд в будущее – 2020 г. - С . 398-401
2. Ёш болаларда кечадиган сальмонеллез касаллигида циклик нуклотидларнинг клиник ва патогенстик ахамияти ММ Мирисмаилов, БМ Таджиев, ФА Рашидов - Re-Health Journa 2020 г. С.389-391 2020 г
3. Болаларда антибиотикларга чидамли сальмонелла тифимуриум чакирган сальмонеллез хасталигининг кечиши
М. М. Мирисмоилов, Ф. А. Рашидов Журнал Биомедицины И Практики 6 (3),2021 г. С. 235-240
4. Исследование реологических свойств крови при сальмонеллезе на Фоне torch-инфекций Мирисмаилов М.М., Рашидов Ф.А., Рихсиева Г.М.«Тиббиётда янги кун» 3 (65) 2024г , С.196-199
5. Acute Intestinal Infections In Children Associated With Candidiasis Infection F. Rashidov, G. Rikhsiyeva, M. Mirismoilov... - Science, 4 (1-4) 2025 ,С. 205-209